

Clash, containment and adjacency detection functions on oriented polygon sets using binary space partitioning trees

1. Introduction

This document presents the mathematical foundations and algorithms for detecting three types of geometric relationships between pairs of sets of polygons in a three-dimensional space. The examined relationships are clash, containment, and adjacency. Polygon sets, which may be open or closed, represent the boundary surfaces of polyhedra. The algorithms introduced here were originally published in [1], with Algorithms 3 and 4 featuring updates from the initial version in that publication. The document begins with a nomenclature, followed by definitions of geometric representations, geometric operators, and finally the functions for detecting clash, containment, and adjacency.

1.1. Nomenclature

This document uses mathematical notations and symbols that are summarized in the following Table 1.

Table 1: Nomenclature

Symbol	Description
BSP	Boundary Space Partition
B-rep	Boundary Representation
\mathbf{A}	Polyhedron or set of polygon sets $\mathbf{A} = \{\mathcal{A}_i\}$
$\partial\mathbf{A}$	Boundary surface representation (B-rep) of polyhedron \mathbf{A}
$T_{\mathbf{A}}$	BSP tree representation of polyhedron \mathbf{A}
A_i	Polygon or line segment set A_i (capital letter)
\hat{n}_{A_i}	Normal vector of polygon $A_i \in \partial\mathbf{A}$ pointing outside \mathbf{A}
\mathcal{A}	Polygon set \mathcal{A} (calligraphic capital letter)
$\uparrow\downarrow$	Opposite direction vectors
$\uparrow\uparrow$	Same direction vectors
$(-)_p$	Coplanar polygon subtraction operation.
\cap_p	Coplanar polygon intersection operation.
\cup	Regular union set operation.

2. Geometric representations

Two types of geometric representation are used in this appendix. The first required geometric representation is the boundary representation B-rep [2] described in Section 2.1. The second is a binary tree representation called the binary space partitioning BSP-tree representation [3], which is described in Section 2.2. Both BSP-tree and B-rep geometrical representations of solid objects are well-studied topics, and efficient transformation algorithms from one form to the other have been developed [4], [5].

2.1. Boundary representation

The B-rep of a polyhedron \mathbf{A} associated with a building entity is denoted by $\partial\mathbf{A}$. Essentially, $\partial\mathbf{A}$ is a set of boundary polygon surfaces $\partial\mathbf{A} = \{A_1, \dots, A_i, \dots, A_N\}$ (see figure 1). Each boundary polygon surface in this representation conforms to the right-hand outward normal convention: the direction of the normal vector \hat{n}_{A_i} of every boundary polygon A_i evaluated using the right-hand side is towards the exterior of the polyhedron \mathbf{A} , as displayed in figure 1. The right-hand normal vector direction evaluation method proceeds as follows: when the fingers of the right hand, excluding the thumb, follow the points of the polygon A_i , the thumb points to the direction of the normal vector. Consequently, the outward normal convention, with the direction of the normal vectors evaluated using the right hand, requires the boundary polygon points to be correctly ordered: in a counterclockwise manner when looking from outside the polyhedron (as displayed in figure 1).

Figure 1: Boundary representation (B-rep) of a polyhedron as a set of boundary polygon surfaces $\partial\mathbf{A} = \{A_1, \dots, A_i, \dots, A_N\}$. When the points of each polygon surface A_i are correctly ordered (counterclockwise when looking from outside the polyhedron), the direction of the normal vector of the surface \hat{n}_{A_i} , evaluated using the right hand, is towards the exterior of the polyhedron.

2.2. Binary Space Partitioning tree representation

A Binary Space Partitioning tree representation or BSP tree [3] generally refers to a set of surfaces \mathcal{A} and is denoted by $T_{\mathcal{A}}$. Since most of the surface sets encountered here are B-reps, the respective BSP trees refer to polyhedrons \mathbf{A} and are denoted by $T_{\mathbf{A}}$, instead of $T_{\partial\mathbf{A}}$ for simplicity.

An example of a BSP-tree referring to an intersection surface set $\mathcal{A}_I \subset \partial\mathbf{A}$ of a polyhedron \mathbf{A} , is displayed in figure 2. In a broad sense, $T_{\mathbf{A}}$ contains the boundary polygons of $\partial\mathbf{A}$ and defines a partition of the 3D space into a finite set of sub-spaces, depending on the orientation of the polyhedron's boundary surfaces. In a broad sense, a BSP tree of a polyhedron is a binary tree that partitions the 3D space into a finite number of sub-spaces according to the outward normal vectors of its boundary surfaces, as described below.

$T_{\mathbf{A}}$ is a structure with three fields. The root value of a BSP tree $T_{\mathbf{A}}$ contains a single root polygon or multiple root coplanar polygons with identical normal vectors and is denoted by the field pol ($T_{\mathbf{A}}.pol$). The plane of the root divides the 3D space into two subspaces, the outside and the inside subspaces. The outside subspace is indicated by the common normal vector of the root polygon(s). The outside subspace contains polygons, which are placed in the right sub-tree of $T_{\mathbf{A}}$ and are denoted by the field $T_{\mathbf{A}}.out$. The inside subspace is indicated by the opposite of the normal vector of the root polygon(s). The inside subspace contains polygons, which are placed in the left sub-tree of $T_{\mathbf{A}}$, and are denoted by the field $T_{\mathbf{A}}.ins$.

Consequently, moving from the root to the leaves of the tree and following the left/right branches lead to inside/outside subspaces (opposite/towards the direction of the outward normal vectors), respectively. The final partitions (sub-regions) of the 3D space are indicated by

the leaves of the tree, which contain binary values. By convention, a leaf has a value of 1 if the respective sub-region is inside the polygons of the node above the leaf and a value of 0 if the respective sub-region lies outside these polygons.

Figure 2: BSP-tree representation of an intersection surface set $\mathcal{A}_I = \{A_1, \dots, A_7\} \subset \partial\mathbf{A}$ of a polyhedron \mathbf{A} creating a non-convex region.

If two boundary polygons are coplanar but their outward normal vectors have opposite directions, one polygon is considered to lie outside the other and, therefore, is placed in separate root nodes. The sequence of the boundary polygons of $\partial\mathbf{A}$, used to populate the BSP tree $T_{\mathbf{A}}$, does not matter. The tree representation $T_{\mathbf{A}}$ of a polyhedron \mathbf{A} is obtained from its B-rep representation $\partial\mathbf{A}$ using the recursive algorithm described in [6].

3. Geometric operations

The geometric operations of the detection algorithms use three geometric filtering functions. These filtering functions are applied on polyhedral pairs \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} and use: the B-reps $\partial\mathbf{A} = \{A_1, \dots, A_{N_{\partial\mathbf{A}}}\}$ and $\partial\mathbf{B} = \{B_1, \dots, B_{N_{\partial\mathbf{B}}}\}$ (with $N_{\partial\mathbf{A}}$, $N_{\partial\mathbf{B}}$ the cardinalities of the sets $\partial\mathbf{A}$, $\partial\mathbf{B}$), as well as the respective BSP-tree representations $T_{\mathbf{A}}$ and $T_{\mathbf{B}}$. These operations are described in the following sections. Additionally, these operations use two *polygon clipping operators* (c_1 and c_2) and a *polygon set partition function*, which are described next.

3.1. Polygon clipping operators

Polygon clipping operators c_1 and c_2 involve two polygons A_i and B_j . Essentially, c_1 and c_2 modify their second operand (polygon A_i), depending on the relative position of their first operand (polygon B_j) and the direction of its normal vector \hat{n}_{B_j} (see figure 3).

Mathematically, these operations are defined by:

$$A_{1i} = B_j(c_1)A_i \text{ and } A_{2i} = B_j(c_2)A_i \quad (1)$$

Generally, three clipping cases can be distinguished:

- A. The plane of B_j *dissects* A_i into two parts: A_{1i} towards the normal vector \hat{n}_{B_j} and A_{2i} towards the opposite direction $-\hat{n}_{B_j}$. This dissection is performed by c_1 or c_2 , returning A_{1i} or A_{2i} , respectively ($A_i = A_{1i} \cup A_{2i}$).

- B1. The plane of B_j dissects the plane of A_i into two half-planes and A_i is in the half-space pointed by \hat{n}_{B_j} . In this case, c_1 returns A_i and c_2 returns an empty set.
- B2. The plane of B_j dissects the plane of A_i into two half-planes and A_i is in the half-space pointed by $-\hat{n}_{B_j}$. In this case, c_1 returns an empty set, and c_2 returns A_i .

The previous clipping operations are implemented using 2D set operations on polygons (intersection, union, and subtraction), following the algorithm proposed in [7].

Figure 3: Illustration of polygon clipping operators c_1 and c_2 on polygon A_i by polygon B_j .

3.2. Polygon set partition function

The polygon set partition function P , used by the geometric clipping functions, can be defined as a partition of a polygon set \mathcal{A} , intersected by a set of coplanar polygons (partition set \mathcal{B}) with the same outward normal vector \hat{n}_B (see figure 4).

Figure 4: Illustration of the polygon set partition function

Mathematically, the polygon set partition function P is defined by the following expression:

$$[\mathcal{A}_{ins}, \mathcal{A}_{csd}, \mathcal{A}_{cod}, \mathcal{A}_{out}] = P(\mathcal{B}, \mathcal{A}) \quad (2)$$

The returning arguments \mathcal{A}_{ins} and \mathcal{A}_{out} are subsets of the set \mathcal{A} containing polygons lying in the half-space pointed by $-\hat{n}_B$ and \hat{n}_B , respectively. \mathcal{A}_{cod} and \mathcal{A}_{csd} contain polygons coplanar with the polygons in \mathcal{B} , which have the opposite (cod) and same direction (csd) normals with \hat{n}_B , respectively (see figure 4). The above sets are populated using Algorithm 1 and the polygon clipping operators c_1 and c_2 .

Algorithm 1 Partition function $P(\mathcal{B}, \mathcal{A})$

```

 $\mathcal{A} = \{A_1, \dots, A_N\}$  // Polygon set (to be partitioned) //
 $\mathcal{B} = \{B_1, \dots, B_M\}$  // Polygon set (partitioning set) //
 $\mathcal{A}_{ins} = \emptyset, \mathcal{A}_{csd} = \emptyset, \mathcal{A}_{cod} = \emptyset, \mathcal{A}_{out} = \emptyset$  // Initialize output sets //
for  $i = 1 : N$  do
  if  $A_i \in \mathcal{A}, B_1$  are coplanar then
    for  $j = 1 : M$  do
       $A_i \leftarrow A_i(-)_p B_j$  // Subtract  $B_j$  from  $A_i$  and update  $A_i$  //
       $AIB_{ij} = A_i \cap_p B_j$  // Intersect  $B_j$  with  $A_i$  and form  $AIB_{ij}$  polygon //
      if  $\hat{n}_{A_i} \uparrow \uparrow \hat{n}_{B_j}$  then
         $\mathcal{A}_{csd} \leftarrow \mathcal{A}_{csd} \cup AIB_{ij}$  // Include polygon  $AIB_{ij}$  in  $\mathcal{A}_{csd}$  set //
      else
         $\mathcal{A}_{cod} \leftarrow \mathcal{A}_{cod} \cup AIB_{ij}$  // Include polygon  $AIB_{ij}$  in  $\mathcal{A}_{cod}$  set //
      end if
    end for
     $\mathcal{A}_{out} \leftarrow \mathcal{A}_{out} \cup A_i$  // Include polygon  $A_i$  in  $\mathcal{A}_{out}$  set //
  else
     $\mathcal{A}_{ins} \leftarrow \mathcal{A}_{ins} \cup [B_1(c_2)A_i]$  // Include clipped polygon  $[B_1(c_2)A_i]$  in  $\mathcal{A}_{ins}$  set //
     $\mathcal{A}_{out} \leftarrow \mathcal{A}_{out} \cup [B_1(c_1)A_i]$  // Include clipped polygon  $[B_1(c_1)A_i]$  in  $\mathcal{A}_{out}$  set //
  end if
end for

```

3.3. Polygon set clipping functions

Using the operators c_1 , c_2 , and the polygon partition function P , four recursive clipping functions F_{ins} , F_{out} , F_{cod} and F_{csd} are defined. These functions are applied on a polygon set \mathcal{A} (clipped polygon set), using the BSP-tree representation T_B of a polyhedron \mathbf{B} (clipping polyhedron). These clipping functions return the polygons or polygon parts of \mathcal{A} , which are:

- Inside polyhedron \mathbf{B} ($\mathcal{A}_{ins} = F_{ins}(T_{\mathbf{B}}, \mathcal{A})$).
- Outside polyhedron \mathbf{B} ($\mathcal{A}_{out} = F_{out}(T_{\mathbf{B}}, \mathcal{A})$).
- Coplanar to polygons of $\partial\mathbf{B}$ with opposite normal vectors ($\mathcal{A}_{cod} = F_{cod}(\partial\mathbf{B}, \mathcal{A})$).
- Coplanar to polygons of $\partial\mathbf{B}$ with same direction normal vectors ($\mathcal{A}_{csd} = F_{csd}(\partial\mathbf{B}, \mathcal{A})$).

Similar to the above, functions have also been used in [6] to perform boolean operations on polyhedra. Function F_{ins} is described by Algorithm 2, function F_{out} by Algorithm 3, function F_{cod} by Algorithm 4 and finally, function F_{csd} by Algorithm 5. In these algorithms, the clipping BSP-tree $T_{\mathbf{B}}$ has three fields: $T_{\mathbf{B}}.pol$ refers to the polygons contained in the root of $T_{\mathbf{B}}$; $T_{\mathbf{B}}.ins$ contains the left (inside) sub-tree of $T_{\mathbf{B}}$; and $T_{\mathbf{B}}.out$ contains the right (outside) sub-tree of $T_{\mathbf{B}}$.

Examples of the clipping functions F_{out} , F_{ins} , F_{cod} and F_{csd} , applied on a polygon set \mathcal{A} , using a clipping polyhedron \mathbf{B} , are displayed in figure 5.

Figure 5: Results of clipping functions – \mathcal{A} is the polygon set of a clipped polyhedron and \mathbf{B} is the clipping polyhedron

Algorithm 2 *Inside clipping function* F_{ins} : $\mathcal{A}_{ins} = F_{ins}(T_{\mathbf{B}}, \mathcal{A})$

```

if  $T_{\mathbf{B}}$  is binary then
  if  $T_{\mathbf{B}} = 0$  then
     $\mathcal{A}_{ins} = \emptyset$  // Initialize output set  $\mathcal{A}_{ins}$  //
  end if
  if  $T_{\mathbf{B}} = 1$  then
     $\mathcal{A}_{ins} = \mathcal{A}$  // Initialize output set  $\mathcal{A}_{ins}$  with  $\mathcal{A}$  //
  end if
else
   $[\mathcal{A}_{p,ins}, \mathcal{A}_{p,csd}, \mathcal{A}_{p,cod}, \mathcal{A}_{p,out}] = P(T_{\mathbf{B}}.pol, \mathcal{A})$  // Partition  $\mathcal{A}$  with  $T_{\mathbf{B}}.pol$  //
  if  $\mathcal{A}_{p,ins} \neq \emptyset$  then
     $\mathcal{A}_{i,ins} = F_{ins}(T_{\mathbf{B}}.ins, \mathcal{A}_{p,ins})$  // Apply  $F_{ins}$  recursively on  $\mathcal{A}_{p,ins}$  with  $T_{\mathbf{B}}.ins$  //
     $\mathcal{A}_{ins} \leftarrow \mathcal{A}_{ins} \cup \mathcal{A}_{i,ins}$  // Include  $\mathcal{A}_{i,ins}$  in  $\mathcal{A}_{ins}$  //
  end if
  if  $\mathcal{A}_{p,out} \neq \emptyset$  then
     $\mathcal{A}_{i,out} = F_{ins}(T_{\mathbf{B}}.out, \mathcal{A}_{p,out})$  // Apply  $F_{ins}$  recursively on  $\mathcal{A}_{p,out}$  with  $T_{\mathbf{B}}.out$  //
     $\mathcal{A}_{ins} \leftarrow \mathcal{A}_{ins} \cup \mathcal{A}_{i,out}$  // Include  $\mathcal{A}_{i,out}$  in  $\mathcal{A}_{ins}$  //
  end if
end if

```

Algorithm 3 *Outside clipping function* F_{out} : $\mathcal{A}_{out} = F_{out}(T_{\mathbf{B}}, \mathcal{A})$

```

if  $T_{\mathbf{B}}$  is binary then
  if  $T_{\mathbf{B}} = 0$  then
     $\mathcal{A}_{out} = \mathcal{A}$  // Initialize output set  $\mathcal{A}_{out}$  with  $\mathcal{A}$  //
  end if
  if  $T_{\mathbf{B}} = 1$  then
     $\mathcal{A}_{out} = \emptyset$  // Initialize output set  $\mathcal{A}_{out}$  //
  end if
else
   $[\mathcal{A}_{p,ins}, \mathcal{A}_{p,csd}, \mathcal{A}_{p,cod}, \mathcal{A}_{p,out}] = P(T_{\mathbf{B}}.pol, \mathcal{A})$  // Partition  $\mathcal{A}$  with  $T_{\mathbf{B}}.pol$  //
  if  $\mathcal{A}_{p,ins} \neq \emptyset$  then
     $\mathcal{A}_{o,ins} = F_{out}(T_{\mathbf{B}}.ins, \mathcal{A}_{p,ins})$  // Apply  $F_{out}$  recursively on  $\mathcal{A}_{p,ins}$  with  $T_{\mathbf{B}}.ins$  //
     $\mathcal{A}_{out} \leftarrow \mathcal{A}_{out} \cup \mathcal{A}_{o,ins}$  // Include  $\mathcal{A}_{o,ins}$  in  $\mathcal{A}_{out}$  //
  end if
  if  $\mathcal{A}_{p,out} \neq \emptyset$  then
     $\mathcal{A}_{o,out} = F_{out}(T_{\mathbf{B}}.out, \mathcal{A}_{p,out})$  // Apply  $F_{out}$  recursively on  $\mathcal{A}_{p,out}$  with  $T_{\mathbf{B}}.out$  //
     $\mathcal{A}_{out} \leftarrow \mathcal{A}_{out} \cup \mathcal{A}_{o,out}$  // Include  $\mathcal{A}_{o,out}$  in  $\mathcal{A}_{out}$  //
  end if
end if

```

Algorithm 4 *Coplanar opposite direction clipping function*

F_{cod} : $\mathcal{A}_{cod} = F_{cod}(\partial\mathbf{B}, \mathcal{A})$

```

for  $A \in \mathcal{A}$  do
  for  $B \in \partial\mathbf{B}$  do
    if  $A, B$  are coplanar and  $\hat{n}_A \uparrow \downarrow \hat{n}_B$  then
       $\mathcal{A}_{cod} \leftarrow \mathcal{A}_{cod} \cup (A \cap_p B)$  // Include the intersection polygon  $A \cap_p B$  in set  $\mathcal{A}_{cod}$  //
    end if
  end for
end for

```

Algorithm 5 *Coplanar same direction clipping function*

 $F_{csd}: \mathcal{A}_{csd} = F_{csd}(\partial\mathbf{B}, \mathcal{A})$

```
for  $A \in \mathcal{A}$  do
  for  $B \in \partial\mathbf{B}$  do
    if  $A, B$  are coplanar and  $\hat{n}_A \uparrow\uparrow \hat{n}_B$  then
       $\mathcal{A}_{csd} \leftarrow \mathcal{A}_{csd} \cup (A \cap_p B)$  // Include the intersection polygon  $A \cap_p B$  in set  $\mathcal{A}_{csd}$  //
    end if
  end for
end for
```

4. Clash and Containment detection

Using the previous definitions, the detection process of a geometric clash among polyhedral geometric representations \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} of a pair of elements, is a function that returns a clash surface set \mathcal{C}_L and is performed using the following algorithmic procedure:

Algorithm 6 *Clash and Containment detection algorithmic process*

```
clash = false
 $\mathcal{C}_L = \emptyset$ 
if  $F_{ins}(T_{\mathbf{B}}, \partial\mathbf{A}) \neq \emptyset$  then
  if  $F_{ins}(T_{\mathbf{A}}, \partial\mathbf{B}) \neq \emptyset$  then
    clash=true // Polyhedron  $\mathbf{A}$  intersects with polyhedron  $\mathbf{B}$  (Regular non-containment clash) //
  else
    clash=true // Polyhedron  $\mathbf{A}$  is contained inside polyhedron  $\mathbf{B}$  (Containment clash) //
  end if
else
  if  $F_{out}(T_{\mathbf{A}}, \partial\mathbf{B}) = \emptyset$  then
    clash=true // Polyhedron  $\mathbf{B}$  is contained inside polyhedron  $\mathbf{A}$  (Containment clash) //
  end if
end if
if clash=true then
   $\mathcal{C}_L = F_{ins}(T_{\mathbf{B}}, \partial\mathbf{A}) \cup F_{csd}(\partial\mathbf{A}, \partial\mathbf{B}) \cup F_{ins}(T_{\mathbf{A}}, \partial\mathbf{B})$  // Clash surface set calculation //
end if
```

According to the algorithm 6, to determine a regular clash (not containment), the F_{ins} filtering function is applied twice: on the B-rep of \mathbf{A} ($\partial\mathbf{A}$), using the BSP-tree of \mathbf{B} ($T_{\mathbf{B}}$) and vice-versa:

$$\mathcal{A}_{ins} = F_{ins}(T_{\mathbf{B}}, \partial\mathbf{A}) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{B}_{ins} = F_{ins}(T_{\mathbf{A}}, \partial\mathbf{B}) \quad (3)$$

If $\mathcal{A}_{ins} \neq \emptyset$ and $\mathcal{B}_{ins} \neq \emptyset$ then a regular clash involving the polyhedrons \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} is detected. The containments, which are special clash cases, are detected in the algorithm 6 by checking whether either $\mathcal{A}_{out} = F_{out}(T_{\mathbf{A}}, \partial\mathbf{B})$ or $\mathcal{B}_{out} = F_{out}(T_{\mathbf{B}}, \partial\mathbf{A})$ are empty. If $\mathcal{A}_{out} = \emptyset$ then \mathbf{A} is inside \mathbf{B} , and if $\mathcal{B}_{out} = \emptyset$, \mathbf{B} is inside \mathbf{A} .

5. Adjacency detection

Using the previous definitions, the detection process of a geometric adjacency among the polyhedral boundary representations $\partial\mathbf{A}$ and $\partial\mathbf{B}$ of a pair of elements \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} , is implemented

using the F_{cod} function (with \mathcal{A} replaced by $\partial\mathbf{A}$), that returns an adjacency surface set \mathcal{A}_D :
 $\mathcal{A}_D = F_{cod}(\partial\mathbf{B}, \partial\mathbf{A})$

References

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